

WP15

Innovation, Impact and Exploitation

ISBE WP15 REPORT

Establish a pipeline(s) for translation of suitable
technologies and methodologies

D 15.3

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Project ref. no.	INFRA-2012-2.2.4: 312455
Project title	ISBE – Infrastructure for Systems Biology Europe
	O= Other
Contractual date of delivery	Month 36
Actual date of delivery	Month 36
Deliverable number	D15.3
Deliverable title	Establish a pipeline(s) for translation of suitable technologies and methodologies
Dissemination Level	PU
Status & version	Final
Number of pages	18
WP relevant to deliverable	WP15
Lead Participant	NUID UCD Eadaoin Mc Kiernan
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Dissemination level: PU = Public, RE = Restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including Commission services), PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including Commission Services), CO= Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)

Nature of Deliverable: P= Prototype, R= Report, D=Demonstrator, O = Other.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Collaboration is a key aspect of systems biology, with multidisciplinary international research teams working across academia and industry. A research infrastructure for systems biology must foster and ease collaborative research, identifying potential obstacles and putting in place mechanisms with which to address them.

This report describes the ways in which companies that utilise systems biology in their operations currently interact with other stakeholders. The report goes on to focus on the issue of intellectual property management, identifying current best practices and potential ways IP could be managed through Infrastructure for Systems Biology Europe.

The report is based on the results from the ISBE industry survey (detailed in D15.1), designed and executed by ISC Intelligence, a Brussels-based communication agency specialising in science, technology and R&D research and policy, in collaboration with University College Dublin. Further interviews were carried out with European Research Infrastructures including EATRIS and EU-SCREEN to identify the IP models they have implemented. These infrastructures were very open to sharing how their IP policies and to continue working on identify further synergies in other fields.

The responses of the various stakeholders in relation to intellectual property are outlined as well as some suggestions on how best manage IP in research projects. All of the companies who took part in the industry survey were asked an open question regarding their IPR policy. The question was “Can you describe your intellectual property policy when your company collaborates with others in research projects?” Fourteen of the organisations responded to the question with the respondents ranging from SMEs up to large multinational organisations across the bioinformatics and pharma sectors.

The meaning of patenting in Systems Biology is still difficult to define, as the area itself is new. Patenting by its own definition applies more to entities that are fixed, static and excluded from the external intervention. This is far from the dynamic and interactive complexity that is the object of the study in systems biology. Most of the patents referred in the survey are mainly computer-based models of biological systems.

2. COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH BY COMPANIES UTILISING SYSTEMS BIOLOGY

The ISBE industry survey (detailed in ISBE D15.1) mapped the collaborative activities of companies utilising systems biology approaches in their operations. All of the organisations surveyed indicated that they do take part in some form of collaboration with other organisations when they carry out research, be that with academia, other industry partners or contract research organisations (CROs) who are contracted to carry out research for other companies.

Figure 1 – Collaboration with other sectors (academia, CROs, industry)

Almost all those interviewed collaborated with academia, 60% collaborated with other industrial companies and 20% collaborated with CROs. A common problem for some SMEs was in forming collaborations with academic institutions, reflected in the slightly lower rate percentage than large organisations. SMEs interviewed indicated that guidance on this from ISBE could have a significant impact on their research. Large organisations are also more likely to collaborate with CROs.

3. CHALLENGES FOR INDUSTRY

The ISBE industry survey identified a range of potential outputs from industrial R&D activities in systems biology. Publication of papers formed the highest proportion, while enhanced collaboration (70%) and registration of a patent (63% of all respondents) were also common outputs.

Figure 2 – R&D outputs from Systems Biology approach

Of the SMEs interviewed 50% started that they have patents as an R&D output where as 80% of the large multinational companies interviewed have patents as an R&D output.

Barriers to innovation

With the emphasis on collaborative research and outputs that require some kind of intellectual property management, it is understandable that when asked about barriers to innovation, concerns about proprietary research were relatively high (56%) while 63% indicated that there was a general lack of knowledge of existing resources.

Barriers to innovation

Figure 3 – Barriers to innovation

With regards to a lack of knowledge of existing resources; companies surveyed felt that they are not fully aware of the products and services that can be accessed to further their systems biology projects as this information is not widely available or publicised.

A number of companies, particularly SMEs stated that if information about which academics are working on certain projects was freely available this would help them to target their engagement with academics most able to accelerate research and boost collaboration.

SMEs interviewed suggested that regulatory guidance on issues around proprietary research and intellectual property management would be very beneficial to their operations. There was also concern expressed by some companies about the types of safety features that the infrastructure may have to ensure that data is not stolen by outside parties.

4. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY IN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

There are a number of choices to be made when choosing an IP strategy for an infrastructure such as ISBE. An appropriate balance must be achieved between making sure that an incentive is given to parties to carry out research by receiving some form of intellectual property right on their work while at the same time not hindering innovation as a whole by overly restrictive intellectual property rights.

IPR can encourage commercialisation by giving an incentive to the creators of intellectual property to create new products and methods as their work is safeguarded from being copied by competitors. IPR can also increase knowledge if the licensing is not too restrictive as it can allow the sharing of information where the creator of the IP gets some form of compensation whether that is money, services or other forms of IP for their work. If the correct IP models and best practices are implemented research would be greatly accelerated with breakthroughs in key areas such as health, agriculture and ICT which would lead to economic growth due to the commercial applications of these breakthroughs.

An open-access IP strategy should boost the generation of data and stimulate new research and products. Novel IPR options must secure rapid knowledge sharing while still allowing fair participation in its exploitation. This strategy must guarantee that “inventors” retain their rights whilst also encouraging industry to invest capital in the development of products based on these disclosures.

These choices range from having no/very little IPR with very high innovation to strong IPR with hindered innovation. There are a number of options between these extremes and these can be tailored to suit a range of scenarios between parties.

The option of having a very open access model would be an accelerant to scientific research as it encourages sharing of knowledge and expertise which ultimately leads to breakthroughs. On the other hand there is very little incentive for companies to take part in this kind of model especially if they are an SME where their data is one of their main assets and it would be a commercial loss to do so. Having little or no IPR tends to be a good idea for the academic community as they are more concerned with publishing and sharing results to further research instead of trying to make a commercial gain from it.

Strong IPR is at the other end of the scale and promotes the protection of knowledge and expertise generated by a stakeholder while at the same time hindering innovation due to other parties needing to pay to use this intellectual property.

5. IP STRATEGIES IDENTIFIED

From the industry survey it was possible to identify certain patterns in the IP arrangements depending on the type of organisation involved (SME, general industry and large industry) and the type of research collaboration between organisations (industrial contract, research collaboration or creating a new company).

5.1. By type of industry

5.1.1. SMEs

Most SMEs need some form of IPR as the data and knowledge that they generate would be one of their main assets. Therefore it would not make economic sense to just give this IP away to other organisations that would have the resources to achieve commercial outputs as a result of the IP that the SMEs have generated. SMEs would find some form of regulatory advice from ISBE useful as they do not have the capacity within the company to cover this field.

5.1.2. Large Multinationals

In some of the larger multinational companies they have the financial resources to pay for the IP associated with the interpretation of their data as well as the methodology developed to analyze the data, for example the models developed for, or using, the large multinationals' data. This cost more for the large multination than it would if they shared the IP with their collaborators, but they forecast that by protecting this IP they will make larger profits in the future. This is beneficial to large companies but it hinders further research due to others not having access to the results and methodologies which leads to duplications of work being carried out.

5.1.3. General industry

Industry on a whole is mainly interested in the profits it can make. Since IP is seen as an area where industry can profit they tend to prefer strong IPR to safeguard their interests. Large organisations understand that the best way to make new commercial outputs involves working with other outside parties. This involves some form of agreement being formed between organisations as to who has the rights to the foreground IP generated in a project and usually involves some sort of trade-off between the partners.

5.2. By type of collaboration

5.2.1. Industrial contract in Systems Biology

This is a contract to deliver a service. The party is paid for carrying out a particular task and the final input belongs in full to the client. However the client is not granted access to the analytical platform and the methodological improvements to the analytical procedures as well as the model generated to achieve the task remain the sole property of the service provider.

1. Contract between bioinformatics and academia/CRO. Bioinformatics companies hire academia to enhance the quality of systems biology modelling or access additional data. Bioinformatics companies will search for complementary expertise and data in hospitals, clinicians, etc. Example of Nova Discovery. Another example is E-therapeutics Company where they collaborate with Oxford University who provided the expertise of treating Parkinson and after they develop the modelling based on the data provided. These bioinformatics companies are usually SMEs that provide specific services to big pharma by developing new methods and algorithms. SMEs might subcontract other SMEs in case need additional expertise.

2. Contract between bioinformatics and industry. Bioinformatics companies develop, for example, the modes of action of a drug and will reveal or predict undesirable side effects and propose novel combinatorial therapeutic approaches. The modelling results and discoveries belong to the industrial client and the models remain exclusive property of the bioinformatics company. GSK for example collaborates with others in clinical trial studies, which generates a lot of data given to a company to interpret. The analysis partner keeps the modelling/methodology but GSK keeps the data as IP.

3. Contract between industry (no bioinformatics but agro or pharma) and academia/CRO. Industry will hire academia to develop data modelling and prediction using academic expertise in machine learning and mathematics. For example Syngenta – the tomato flavour project. Another type of collaboration is when the industry provides data and academia and CROs will develop methods, workflows and tools to analyse the data. This will have an impact in establishing clinical trials methodology, patients' statistics, identify biomarkers, etc.

4. Contract between industry (agro or pharma) and industry. This is related to big pharma using highly specialised SMEs providing services in a specific niche. Companies such Pfizer use SMEs for modelling generation, etc. Sometimes the pharma industry will hire an SME for data interpretation and the pharma industry provides data and modelling. When bioinformatics are integrated into pharma they own IP and licence to each other.

5.2.2. Research collaboration

When organisations get together and create a partnership to carry out a research project, where each partner pays his own cost, the IP addressing patentable discoveries is shared on the basis of relative contribution to the discovery. Each partner is given free access to the models generated but ownership of the models is retained by the bioinformatics company.

For example, BM systems develop modelling and use academia for data experimentation and generation to prove the model.

5.2.3. *Creating new company dedicated to the exploitation and commercialisation*

The IP related to creating a new company as a result of a research project. Two different approaches depend on the status of the IP:

1. IP results from the internal research activities of a company and is fully owned by them. The company then transfers the patent ownership to the new company in return for a share amounting to at least 45% of the total equity of the new company. The new company is not granted access to the analytical platform, and its methodology and analytical procedures, as well as the models constructed to generate the discovery covered by the transferred IP, which remains the sole property of the initial company
2. If the IP results from collaborative work, and is shared, each partner retains an ownership share of the IP and all the partners agree to transfer the IP exploitation rights to the new company in return for royalties and a percentage of benefits from sales.

5.3. IP in another Research Infrastructure: EATRIS

An example of another research infrastructure using IP scenarios to make the position of parties clear would be EATRIS, the European Infrastructure for Translational Medicine. EATRIS had a number of trial runs with universities and private companies such as Roche to gain an understanding of their needs and to develop public-private pathways without negotiations to see how various scenarios worked. They then designed three categories that had a number of principles in each and the companies could pick the categories that best suited their needs. Examples of some of the categories are as follows:

Category 1

This is where industry has a request e.g. they have IP, or a patent etc. that they need assistance researching. All the outcomes of the research belong to industry but academia gets paid more for their work.

Category 2

Here industry comes to the infrastructure with a question that they need help defining. Academia helps with defining the question and follows up on answering the question. Here

the benefits are more evenly distributed because both parties are working on equal terms and usually involved the IP being shared.

Category 3

This is where national authorities/EU institutions want help and they get more allowances from the infrastructure than conventional private companies would.

EATRIS have a few large clients such as Roche but mostly they work with SMEs. They have also done work with semi-private bodies such as charities that are responsible for the dissemination of funds for research. These charities have money for research but don't know how to disseminate it so EATRIS gives advice as to how to spend it and who to contact. An example of this would be when EATRIS went the Netherlands ministry and sought permission which they were granted to talk to the charities and helped them in their search for the right partners. They also find that clients need regulatory advice especially if they are SMEs.

6. CONCLUSIONS: A COMMERCIALISATION PIPELINE FOR ISBE

Systems biology research is driven by collaborations of many kinds, between industry, academia and other organisations. An infrastructure for systems biology should ensure that the intellectual property management of research outputs associated with the infrastructure actively fosters and promotes innovation rather than inhibiting it.

The research outlined in this report has identified a variety of models to managing intellectual property, from open-access IPR strategy to boost the generation of knowledge and stimulate new research and products to restrictive IPR with an emphasis on protecting intellectual property. From our discussions with a range of stakeholders, a blanket 'one size fits all' approach is impossible; instead either negotiating IP on a case by case basis or developing a range of categories and principles for infrastructure users to select would appear to be the most workable options.

A number of recommendations, based on the findings of this report, have been developed to guide the infrastructure as it enters its Interim Phase:

- 1. ISBE as broker of collaborations:** mechanisms are required to bring together industry and academia into mutually beneficial partnerships, both on a project-by-

project basis, and in the longer term. ISBE, with its pan-European reach, should act as the broker of such engagements and put in place resources to support this.

2. **IP Strategy:** An IP strategy should be developed for research outputs associated with the ISBE infrastructure with a focus on fostering and encouraging innovation.
3. **Meeting the IP needs of stakeholders:** A variety of categories of IP management scenarios should be developed to suit the needs of a range of stakeholders and to provide clarity for stakeholders at the outset of their research projects.
4. **Regulatory advice:** There is a clear need for regulatory advice in the area of IP, especially for SMEs. ISBE should put in place resources and services to address this current bottleneck and develop a niche as a provider of information in this area.

ANNEX I – MANAGEMENT OF IPR BY COMPANY

This annex describes the answers of all the industry to the question related to the internal management of Intellectual Property Rights within the company in the ISBE Industry Survey (detailed in D15.1).

BM Systems

At the moment, they apply any one of three possible modes of operation.

- 1) In the context of an industrial contract
- 2) In the context of collaboration, be it academic or industrial, where each partner pays his own costs, the IP addressing patentable discoveries is shared on the basis of relative contribution to the discovery.
- 3) In the context of the creation of new companies (new co) dedicated to the exploitation and commercialisation of one or more of BMS's discoveries, they proceed along two different lines, depending upon the status of the IP.

Syngenta

For Syngenta the IP policy depends on many variables. If it is University collaboration with a research council involved we use the Russell agreement format. Other collaborations with CROs are usually fee for service and we own everything. Partnership collaborations are negotiated on a case by case basis and no single view would cover all. It depends on the background from both parties, the nature of the input and output of the collaboration etc.

Heptares

It depends on the nature of the collaboration. For some partners who act as contract research organisations, all of the intellectual property is owned by us. For others the intellectual property could be owned by either party, and may be subsequently assigned or licensed to the other party.

Biomax

They have a grand agreement which is project-dependent on how background and foreground IP is dealt with. For example, if another partner needs the software or results

from collaboration they have a freedom to use policy which has fair and reasonable licensing conditions.

MediSapiens Ltd

IPR is dealt with on a case by case basis depending on the type of project involved and the needs and wants of the clients.

Genedata

For Genedata, it is important to maintain full ownership of the products (software) that they market. With respect to ownership of results and data, they are open to different models.

For example, their general policy is open to the exploitation of such results by consortium members or third parties, provided there is adequate compensation.

EdgeLeap

The general IP policy is the following: all data technology aspects are EdgeLeap's IP, while all outcomes/findings are client's IP.

Nova Discovery

Done by a case by case basis, it usually depends on the partners' involvement in inventive activities. In a nutshell, they are happy to share any IP in accordance with effective contributions from respective partners'.

GSK vaccines

This Depends on the type of collaboration, for example a clinical study generates data, which GSK gives to an analysis partner (not always a company) to interpret. The analysis partner keeps the methodology/modelling but GSK keeps the data as IP. It should always be taken into account that IP follows the “freedom to operate” which means that IP agreement cannot be so restrictive as to block the research from being carried out.

KinDyn Consulting Ltd

They have a collaboration agreement in place. The client owns all the data and the models produced. KinDyn provides a service to the client for data interpretation and does not own either the raw data or the models which are subsequently produced.

LYO-X GmbH

A consortium of SMEs formed a collaborative agreement where they would provide services for each other in the knowledge that they would receive other services and products in return. This led to an understanding of the strengths that each party could bring to the table, which in turn led to improved innovation and ultimately to more projects being undertaken together in the future. An example of this would be where one SME provides the modelling expertise while the other provides the context with their expertise (asking the right question). These organisations would have decided, in their collaborative agreements, the rights of each of the parties in relation to the foreground IP generated.

Pfizer

This is a complicated matter. It totally depends on the partner and on how the collaboration outputs are handled. Sometimes it is just a publication, on other occasions outcomes are shared with the general public. It depends on whether Pfizer initiates the work, or collaboration, are approached externally, participate in a public consortium like IMI, C-Path, and so on.

Pfizer certainly has many collaborations with academics and other companies, of which the outcomes are not shared externally.

In essence there is no single policy to follow, as it is usually a negotiation taking all partners' interests into account, and if the company does not feel its rights could be honored, it would not collaborate.

MediSapiens

Their policy in these cases is to approach things on a case-by-case basis. As a software company, their main intellectual property is the code and bioinformatic methods they develop. If it is a question of pre-existing software, the typical model used is to grant use of it for a specific predefined purpose, whether academic or commercial. If it is a question of IP developed jointly in the project, it becomes a very case-by-case approach. Much depends on how much both parties contribute to the development.

ISBE Infrastructure
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Europe

KinDyn Consulting Ltd

Contracts are usually written such that any intellectual property arising from a contract becomes the property of the client. As this would usually relate to the project that KinDyn are working on, which is the property of the client, they are happy to accept this clause.

If intellectual property is generated, which could have a more general application, across a wider field then this would need to be discussed with the client.

ANNEX II: PRINCIPLES OF DATA MANAGEMENT FOR BIOLOGICAL AND BIOMEDICAL SCIENCE RIs

Under the umbrella of BioMedBridges, the biomedical sciences research infrastructures involved in the project plus AnaEE, ISBE and MIRRI as well as LifeWatch developed a document on the Principles of data management and sharing at European Research Infrastructures. The document makes key recommendations on how data management and sharing via the research infrastructures can be supported and encouraged:

1. The RIs encourage data sharing and reuse and support the notion that public funders should encourage Open Access to data from publicly funded research where possible.
2. Some data may only be shared under certain conditions and with appropriate safe keeping mechanisms in place, such as personally identifiable data, data subject to ethical or legal restrictions, or restrictions for intellectual property protection.
3. To encourage data sharing, systematic reward and recognition mechanisms are necessary.
4. Proposals for publicly funded research at RIs should include a data management plan concerning the deposition of data in long-term archives that addresses specific resources and activities (including standardisation of data production and curation/annotation).
5. Funding for tools and activities connected to data deposition must be available.
6. Systems, services and resources must be in place to facilitate straightforward data deposition by researchers, including support concerning the necessary data use agreements and consent forms for data with data protection or intellectual property requirements.
7. Systems are also needed to capture and track data provenance and use.
8. To ensure necessary trust by data providers or depositors, RIs must guarantee high standards of security and traceability.